

A survey of progress on rates and mechanisms of reactions of metal complexes[†]

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Introduction

Mechanisms of reactions of metal complexes received the attention of chemists since the days of Alfred Werner who, based entirely on qualitative investigations, had proposed (1912) the possibility of racemization of metal complexes of the type $M(A-A)_3$ (octahedral) by an intramolecular mechanism¹. Research in this area started quite early in the 20th century by Lamb and coworkers² who studied the rates of hydrolysis of several six-coordinate (octahedral) complexes of the type $M(NH_3)_5X^{2+}$ ($M = Co^{III}, Rh^{III}, Ir^{III}$; $X^- = Cl^-, Br^-, I^-$). However, extensive systematic studies emerged from different groups, mostly since the late forties of the last century. During the last five decades there has been an almost explosive growth in the field, significantly more than in any other areas of inorganic chemistry including materials science and bioinorganic chemistry which are also receiving much attention particularly in recent years. Most of the early developments are well documented in several treatises³ and the field is regularly covered since 1971 in annual reviews⁴. Three of the recent reviews are on substitution and redox processes in transition metal complexes^{5a}, a general one on inorganic mechanistic chemistry^{5b} and a short review on reactions of complexes of Pd^{II} and Pt^{II} containing nitrogen donor ligands^{5c} systematic studies of which were first reported by the present author^{5d,e}. Development of medical applications of coordination complexes now continues to be aided by detailed structural and mechanistic studies^{5f,g}. In the present discussion, the major contributions mostly of the later periods up to the end of the last century (2000 AD) will be broadly covered for the various classes of reactions in solutions but because of constraints of space the coverage will not be exhaustive; for convenience and clarity some earlier results will be mentioned as considered necessary with obvious emphasis on the author's own contributions in the field.

Ligand replacement processes

An overall reaction of the type, $M-X + Y \rightarrow M-Y + X$ in solution may be sub-divided into two steps, the first being a diffusional encounter of the reactants followed by a reorganization of the encounter complex (an outer-sphere

complex in the present context) into the products⁶. If the overall rate is more than an order of magnitude slower than the diffusion-controlled limit, the first step may be treated as a pre-equilibrium and the rate-law will correspond to the following mechanism of reaction :

here K_E is the equilibrium constant for formation of the encounter complex and k the first-order rate constant for the rate-determining reorganization step leading to another outer-sphere species with X being in the outer-sphere of the product complex $M-Y$. For an octahedral complex M stands for a species such as MA_5 of coordination number (C.N.) 5, where A is a spectator ligand which does not undergo replacement under the conditions for replacement of X , but which influences the rate of replacement of X by Y in various ways as are well-known. The substitution process proceeding through the pathway as represented by eq. (1) is known as *interchange (I)* process^{3b}. An understanding of the outer-sphere complex formation (which is ion-pairing in appropriate cases)⁷ is of importance in such mechanistic studies.

In the *dissociative (D)* process of importance in many ligand substitution an encounter with the entering ligand may not precede but follows the slow step involving $M-X$ bond rupture :

The implication is that M is an intermediate of lower C. N. (5 in case of an octahedral complex of C.N. 6) with a sufficiently long lifetime so that a competition between X and Y for M is possible depending on the relative magnitudes of k_{-1} and k_2 . This is known as the *dissociative (D)* process^{3b}.

Both *I* and *D* processes are of significance for ligand replacement reactions of octahedral complexes. But for the square-planar complexes, such as those of Pd^{II} , Pt^{II} , Au^{III} , etc., which are coordinatively unsaturated, the most important reaction pathway is *associative (A)* process^{3b} and this

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may be represented as follows ($k_2 > k_1$ generally) :

In the interchange (*I*) process (*loc.cit.*) in the transformation of M-X, Y to M-Y, X both M-X bond dissociation and M-Y bond formation are synchronous and depending on which is predominant the *I* processes are sub-divided into I_d and I_a processes respectively^{3b}. The *D*, *A*, I_d and I_a processes correspond to the classical S_N1 (liting), S_N2 (limiting), S_N1 and S_N2 processes, respectively⁸.

In the *A* process when Y is other than the solvent the rate is first order with respect to each of the two reactants M-X and Y, and hence a second order rate law is observed overall. However, the pathways represented by eqs. (1) and (2) also frequently lead to similar second order rate expressions in appropriate systems under appropriate conditions and hence the observed rate law as such does not tell us about the mechanism^{8c}. From an analysis of the various parameters on the rate and several other experimental evidences it is often possible to infer about the most plausible mechanism of the reaction. Broadly speaking these are the effects of charge on the complex, nature of entering and leaving groups, steric effects, effects of spectator (non-labile) ligands, solvent effects, isotope effects, magnitude of ΔH^\ddagger , ΔS^\ddagger and ΔV^\ddagger , stereochemical changes accompanying the reaction, etc.^{3,8}.

Bases hydrolysis is a typical ligand replacement process which involves replacement of a ligand by OH^- , a change generally observed in alkaline solutions. The mechanism of bases hydrolysis has been a subject of much controversy; while evidence has been furnished in support of the *conjugate base (CB) mechanism* $S_N1\text{-CB}$ (i.e., *D-CB*), other alternatives appear feasible in many cases and the field is still of much promise and interest for investigations⁹⁻¹⁴. The bases hydrolysis of $\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{X}^{n+}$ ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}^-, \text{Br}^-, \text{NO}_2^-$ or DMSO) has been studied in presence of N_3^- in solution and the observed product ratio $R = [\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5(\text{N}_3)^{2+}] / [\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5(\text{OH})^{2+}]$ at three different temperatures has been reconciled with I_d mechanism for transformation of the *CB*¹⁵. This differs from the conventional *D-CB* ($S_N1\text{-CB}$) mechanism^{3a} as it does not involve a common intermediate $\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4(\text{NH}_2)^{2+}$ of C.N. = 5 for all the different leaving groups X, but involves a process in which entry of the entering ligands (OH^- and N_3^-) and loss of X are synchronous with predominance of Co-X bond dissociation in forming the transition state. The insensitivity of R to temperature is more in agreement with I_d rather than I_a mechanism. However, convincing evidence for a five-coordinate intermedi-

ate has been furnished in some cases¹⁶. In our earlier investigations we furnished evidence for the operation of different mechanisms such as D ¹⁷, I_a ¹⁸, *D-CB*¹⁹, *A-IP*²⁰ and *D-IP*²¹ in different systems. It has been aptly pointed out by our group¹⁹ that ion-pair (IP) and conjugate base (CB) are the limiting situations of a system $\text{M}(\text{X})(\text{NH}_2^-) \cdots \cdots \text{H}^+ \cdots \cdots \text{OH}^-$. The subtle change in mechanism of bases hydrolysis of $\text{Cr}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{X}^{2+}$ from *D-CB* to *D-IP* as X^- changes from N_3^- to NCS^- has been explained on the basis of the change in nucleophilicity, E_n , of these X^- ligands¹⁹. Similar behavior was reported in the base hydrolysis of *trans*- $\text{Rh}(\text{en})_2\text{X}_2^+$, where the observed rate sequence for different X^- was $\text{I}^- > \text{NCS}^- > \text{N}_3^- > \text{Br}^- > \text{Cl}^-$ with a change over from *D-CB* to *D-IP* at the NCS^- and N_3^- boundary line²². Base hydrolysis of $\text{Ru}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{I}^{2+}$ has been proposed²³ to occur by *A* and *A-CB* processes. Precursor ion-pair formation in the base hydrolysis of cationic complexes having ionizable proton is now well-established²⁴. However, the ion-pair may also react through formation of the much more reactive CB present in equilibrium with the IP²⁵, and in such a situation the rate law is similar to what is expected for direct transformation of the IP into the product²⁶. The greater lability of the CB has been accounted for by the strong donor (sigma and pi) nature of the NH_2 group²⁷. While there is much evidence for generation of the CB by deprotonation of an amine *trans* to the leaving group²⁸, there are arguments²⁹ and evidence³⁰ of deprotonation of amine *cis* to the departing group in some cases. Thus, an insight into the site of deprotonation was obtained by measuring the relative rates of H-D exchange for the amine *cis* and *trans* to X in the complexes like $\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{X}^{n+}$ and *cis*- $\text{Co}(\text{A-A})_2\text{X}_2^{m+}$ ($\text{A-A} = (\text{NH}_3)_2, \text{en}$) in D_2O solvent³⁰. The results indicated that for $\text{X} = \text{CN}^-, \text{NO}_2^-, \text{SO}_3^{2-}$, the exchange of H in the *cis*-amine was faster than for the *trans*-amine, while for $\text{X} = \text{H}_2\text{O}, \text{F}^-, \text{Cl}^-, \text{Br}^-, \text{N}_3^-, \text{MeCO}_2^-, \text{gly}^-, 1/2\text{CO}_3^{2-}, 1/2\text{ox}^{2-}$, etc., the exchange in the *trans*-amine was much faster than for the *cis*-amine³⁰.

Conversion of $\text{Cr}(\text{NH}_3)_5(\text{ONO})^{2+}$ to $\text{Cr}(\text{NH}_3)_5(\text{OH})^{2+}$ in alkaline media occurs by a pseudo-substitution process without Cr-ONO bond rupture²¹. A linear relationship between the activation energies and the ligand field parameter Dq for base hydrolysis of $\text{M}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{I}^{2+}$ type complexes ($\text{M} = \text{Cr}, \text{Co}, \text{Rh}, \text{Ir}$) has been reported³¹; it is interesting to note that a common mechanism seems to be operating in all these systems. Results on base hydrolysis of $\text{Ru}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{X}^{2+}$ and *cis*- $\text{Ru}(\text{en})_2\text{X}_2^+$ ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}, \text{Br}, \text{I}$) fit³² the familiar conjugate base mechanism, *D-CB*.

The steric course of base hydrolysis of geometrical isomers of complexes allows one to make inference about the nature of the mechanism, viz. associative or dissociative,

and as to the structure of the transient intermediate in the reaction, viz. *tbp* or *sp* for a dissociative change³³. For a series of *trans*-Co(en)₂(RCH₂CO₂)Cl⁺ (R = H, Cl, Br, I, CN, NH₂), the electronegative substituents R enhance the acidity of the amine (en) protons and hence also the rate of base hydrolysis as is to be expected for a conjugate base mechanism; the products of base hydrolysis are ca. 71% *trans* and ca. 29% *cis* of the complex Co(en)₂(RCH₂CO₂)-(OH)⁺ which indicates that both *tbp* and *sp* intermediates are involved³⁴, since *trans* to *cis* conversion is very much slower in these complexes than the rates of their base hydrolysis. But base hydrolysis of several Ru^{III} complexes of the type *trans*-Ru(LLLL)X₂⁺ occurs by *CB* mechanism and leads to 100% *trans*-Ru(LLLL)(OH)₂⁺, indicating reaction through a square-pyramidal (*sp*) intermediate³⁵, and not the trigonal-bipyramidal (*tbp*).

The role of ion association by a counter ion and evidence for the formation of a common intermediate of reduced C.N. in the base hydrolysis of Co(NH₃)₅Xⁿ⁺ have been discussed³⁶. Constancy of ΔH_T values for base hydrolysis of several complexes Co(NH₃)X²⁺ (X = Cl, Br, I)³⁷ and significantly positive ΔV^\ddagger values for base hydrolysis of several complexes³⁸ of Co^{III} are consistent with the *D-CB* mechanism. However, for base hydrolysis of Cr(bipy)₃³⁺ an associative mechanism has been suggested³⁹. A conjugate base mechanism seems convincing for the base-catalysed nitrito to nitro isomerization of M(NH₃)₅(ONO)²⁺ (M = Co^{III}, Rh^{III}, Ir^{III})⁴⁰.

Conjugate base mechanism does not agree with the results of base hydrolysis of some (+)-*cis*-Co(en)₂(NH₃)X²⁺ complexes but has been reconciled with ion-pair mechanism⁴¹. Base hydrolysis of M(NH₃)₅(NCS)²⁺ (M = Cr, Co, Rh) in water-ethanol and water-acetone mixed solvents have indicated⁴² significant ion-pair formation as precursor. The dependence of the rate constant on the dielectric constant of the medium and other well-known empirical solvent parameters, viz. *Y*, *Z* and *E*_T, which express the solvating and ionizing power of the solvent (including mixed solvents) have indicated significant associative character in all the cases with more associative character for Co^{III} and Rh^{III} than Cr^{III} in these cases which is broadly in agreement with earlier studies of these in aqueous solutions⁴³. But in general for aquation^{8c} Cr^{III} is more associative than Co^{III}.

Base hydrolysis of Co(NH₃)₅(S₂O₃)⁺ in ethanol-water and acetone-water follows both alkali-independent and alkali-dependent paths⁴⁴. For each of these paths, the values of the rate constants and the corresponding ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger are markedly dependent on solvent polarity, and their correlation with different solvent parameters suggests associa-

tive activation (*I*_a process was concluded in earlier studies in aqueous solutions¹⁸). An *isokinetic relationship* has been observed⁴⁴ between the ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger values for different paths for the base hydrolysis in water and also in the water-ethanol and water-acetone mixed solvents, as also for the replacement of S₂O₃²⁻ in the Co^{III} complex by Cl⁻ and NH₃ in aqueous solutions¹⁸; this suggests operation of similar mechanisms in these reactions. For base hydrolysis of *cis*-Co(cyclam)X₂⁺ (X = Cl, Br; cyclam = 1,4,8,11-tetraazacyclotetradecane)⁴⁵ there is evidence for operation of a concerted *E*₂ mechanism in which cleavage of the N-H bond and Co-X bond occurs synchronously producing the five-coordinate intermediate without the intervention of a six-coordinate conjugate base. The ratio k_{OH}^{Br}/k_{OH}^{Cl} is 9 at 25°. This considerable dependence of the rate on the nature of the analogous leaving groups, viz. Cl⁻ and Br⁻, is not consistent with the conventional *D-CB* mechanism but is consistent with the *E*₂ mechanism.

Complexes of tetrapodal pentaamine ligands, Co(L)Cl²⁺, where L is (a) or 2,6-((H₂NCH₂)₂C(Me))₂C₅H₃N (a disubstituted pyridine) and where the L forms a square-pyramidal coordination cap, behave differently under conditions of base hydrolysis. The complex having the disubstituted pyridine as L is particularly inert to base hydrolysis⁴⁶, which involves a conjugate base mechanism with deprotonation of the amine nitrogen *cis* to the departing Cl⁻. But the rate

constant for base hydrolysis of the complex having L = (a) is 250 times larger⁴⁷ than for Co(NH₃)₅Cl²⁺ due to enhanced *trans-influence* facilitating loss of the Cl⁻ from the *CB* intermediate. When the base hydrolysis is carried out in 1 M NaN₃ only ca. 1% of Co(L)(N₃)₂²⁺ is formed which shows unusually short lifetime for the *CB* in this case. Similar studies⁴⁸ have shown that electron-withdrawing substituents on O-bonded amides (L) in Co(NH₃)₅(L)³⁺ can lead to significant C-O bond cleavage in addition to the Co-O bond fission in base hydrolysis. The two isomeric Co^{III} complexes *endo*- and *exo-mer*-Co(triamine)(diamine)Cl²⁺ (triamine = dien and such others, diamine = en or pn) undergo base hydrolysis with complete retention of the *mer*-configuration

but with some inversion at the *sec*-NH site⁴⁹ Base hydrolysis of $\text{Co}(\text{tetren})(\text{NCR})^{3+}$ ($\text{R} = \text{Me}, \text{Ph}, \text{or } 4\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{OMe})$) involves $S_{\text{N}}1\text{-CB}$ displacement of the nitrile without carboxamide formation⁵⁰

Base hydrolysis of $\text{trans-Pt}(\text{CN})_4\text{Br}_2^{2-}$ is interesting⁵¹, here obviously no conjugate base formation is possible. The observed rate law shows two terms, one dependent on OH^- concentration and the other on Br^- concentration. Large positive ΔS^\ddagger value for the k_{OH} path is in agreement with I_{d} process, while Br^- -dependent path may be explained by Br^- association with the complex through the bound Br^- ligand and thus accounts for the negative ΔS^\ddagger value observed for this k_{Br} path. However, anionic Co^{III} complexes like $\text{Co}(\text{CN})_5\text{X}^{n-}$ ($\text{X}^- = \text{Cl}^-, \text{Br}^-, \text{I}^-, \text{NCS}^-, \text{N}_3^-, \text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}$) undergo base hydrolysis by OH^- -independent dissociative pathway (D process)¹⁷

Base hydrolysis of many of the typical square-planar complexes of Pt^{II} are independent of OH^- concentration due to reaction occurring as follows (with OH^- deprotonating the intermediate aqua-complex)

However, $\text{M}(\text{Et}_4\text{dien})\text{Cl}^{n+}$ ($\text{M} = \text{Pd}^{\text{II}}, \text{Pt}^{\text{II}}$ or Au^{III}) show typical first order dependence on OH^- concentration⁵² due to operation of the usual conjugate base mechanism and these complexes are termed *pseudo-octahedral* as they show the behavior typical of the octahedral complexes⁵²

Replacement of a ligand by H_2O in a metal complex in

aqueous solutions is called *aquation* and is generally observed in acidic solutions. Similar reactions occur in other solvents (S) like DMF, DMSO, MeCN, etc., and the general term for such reactions is *solvolysis*. Rate data are available⁵³ for aquation of the three geometrical isomers (**b-d**) of $\text{Co}(\text{dien})(\text{tmd})\text{Cl}^{2+}$ and the corresponding isomers of $\text{Co}(\text{dien})(\text{en})\text{Cl}^{2+}$. In each of the cases the six-membered ring compound having tmd aquates much faster than its five-membered ring analogue having en in place of tmd. At 25° the ratio $k_{\text{tmd}}/k_{\text{en}}$ is 16.8, 31.7 and 2.3 for (**b**), (**c**) and (**d**), respectively. The increase in rate is ca. 32 times in changing from en to tmd in the Co^{III} complex of structure (**c**), but for the analogous complexes of Cr^{III} the rates are nearly the same. The observed difference in the rate for the Co^{III} complexes is in agreement with a dissociative mechanism involving a *tbp* intermediate which is expected to be formed much more easily by the complex having a six-membered bidentate chelate ring (formed by tmd) compared to the five-membered ring formed by en which is expected to restrict the distortion of the chelate ring needed to form the *tbp* intermediate as this will greatly strain the five-membered chelate ring. But the near identity of the rates for the Cr^{III} complexes is in agreement with associative character of the reaction.

For aquation of $\text{Co}(\text{LL})_2(\text{L})\text{X}^{n+}$ and $\text{Co}(\text{LLL})(\text{LL})\text{X}^{n+}$ (where L, LL and LLL stand for uni-, bi- and terdentate ligands) where X is the leaving group, the plot of $\log k_{\text{aq}}$ vs $\nu_{\text{N-Co-N}}$ (deformation frequency in the IR spectra of the complexes) is linear with a negative slope⁵⁴ which reflects the ease with which these complexes can distort via a deformational vibration mode to form the trigonal-bipyramidal (*tbp*) intermediate of a dissociative mechanism. While ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger values for spontaneous aquation of $\text{M}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Cl}^{2+}$ ($\text{M} = \text{Co}, \text{Cr}$) suggest a common associative (possibly I_{a}) mechanism, computational studies⁵⁵ confirm I_{d} process for Co^{III} and I_{a} process for Cr^{III} , which is in agreement with various other evidences.

The steric course of aquation reactions has been investigated quite extensively and the results provide useful information about the plausible mechanism and structure of the intermediate. The stereochemistry of the products in the spontaneous and Hg^{II} -assisted aquation of (+)-*cis*- $\text{Co}(\text{en})_2(\text{X})\text{Y}^{n+}$ and of the corresponding *trans*-isomers has been re-examined in aqueous HClO_4 solutions for various types of X and Y ligands (halide, azide, hydroxy, DMF, DMSO, etc.). The results have shown that these complexes aquate spontaneously with considerable steric change for both the *cis*- and *trans*-isomers contrary to earlier reports (R. G. Pearson and F. Basolo, 1956) and hence the two isomers are not fundamentally different in their aquation behavior^{53, 56a, b},

since 15–20% conversion to the *trans*-product has been observed in all the cases studied (exact value depends on the nature of X and Y). However, the chiral *cis*-product retains full optical activity and hence the loss of optical activity occurs only by isomerization into the inactive *trans*-isomer^{56a,b}. For most of the (+)-*cis*-Co(en)₂(X)Yⁿ⁺, the steric course of the spontaneous and Hg^{II}-assisted aquations are the same and are independent of the nature of the leaving group^{56a,b}. But for *cis*- and *trans*-Cr(NH₃)₄X₂⁺ (X = Cl, Br) the first step aquation (loss of one X⁻) both for the spontaneous and Hg^{II}-induced processes proceeds with full retention of configuration^{56c} and retention of configuration appears to be the general rule for the aquation reactions of Cr^{III} complexes, suggesting associative reaction involving *cis*-attack.

For aquation of Ru(LLLL)X₂⁺ (LLLL = (NH₃)₄, (en)₂, 2,3,2-tet, cyclam; X = Cl or Br) the *cis* isomer is more labile than the *trans* and the rates decrease with increasing chelation by LLLL in each case and reactivities are determined by solvation, nephelauxetic and *sigma trans*-effects; there is complete retention of stereochemistry indicating a *D* mechanism operating through a square-pyramidal intermediate⁵⁷. Substitution by DMF in Ru(H₂O)₆²⁺ is an I_d process⁵⁸. For aquation of Ru(NH₃)₅Cl²⁺, Δ*V*[‡] = -30 cm³ mol⁻¹ (at 60°) and this high negative value is evidence for an *A* mechanism, being in agreement with other evidences for associative substitution at Ru^{III} centre⁵⁹.

For the substitution process,

M(Cp*)(H₂O)₃ + L → [M(Cp*)(H₂O)₂L]^{x-} (M = Rh or Ir; L = Cl⁻, Br⁻, I⁻, SCN⁻, C₆H₄N(R) (R = H, 4-CN or 3-CO(NH₂)), SC(NH₂)₂ or DMSO; Cp* = C₅(Me)₅) the rate constants are close to that for water exchange showing hardly any dependence on L. This observation, together with the experimentally determined Δ*V*[‡] values, supports a *D* or I_d process⁶⁰. Values of Δ*V*[‡] reveal⁶¹ the importance of electronic rather than steric effects in determining subtle mechanistic shifts I_a to I_d in the spontaneous replacement of DMF or DMA by H₂O in *cis*- and *trans*-[Co(NH₃)₄(MeNH₂) (DMF)]³⁺, *cis*- or *trans*-[Co(L)(DMF)]³⁺ (L = HN{CH₂CH(CH₂NH₂)₂}₂), *cis*-[M(NH₃)₄(L)Cl]²⁺ (M = Cr; L = DMF; M = Co; L = DMA) and *cis*-[M(en)₂(L)Cl]²⁺.

In cases of anionic complexes of M²⁺ and M³⁺ base hydrolysis, aquation and anation (reverse of aquation for anionic ligands) occur through a *D* mechanism and there are fairly convincing evidences in this regard⁶². Values of Δ*V*[‡] for aquation of Co(CN)₅X³⁻ (X = Cl, Br, I) and anation of Co(CN)₅(H₂O)²⁻ are in the range of +8 to +14 cm³ mol⁻¹ (at 40°)⁶³ and the positive values are in agreement with *D* mechanism. One expects dissociative activation in the cases

of anionic complexes since the overall negative charge is expected to favour M-X bond dissociation. Significantly, positive Δ*V*[‡] values for the reaction, Fe(CN)₅L³⁻ + CN⁻ → Fe(CN)₆⁴⁻ + L (L = substituted pyridine)⁶⁴ and for chloride anation⁶⁵ of RuCl₅(H₂O)²⁻ and of *cis*-RhCl₄(H₂O)₂⁻ also support *D* mechanism. From near identity of Δ*S*[‡] values for the stepwise aquation of *trans*-Co(dmgH)₂Cl₂⁻ with the Δ*S* for the hydration of Cl⁻, it has been concluded that both steps of the aquation are dissociative (*D*) in nature⁶⁶, and the same appears to be true for aquation of *cis*-Cr(en)₂Cl₂⁺⁶⁷. However, high positive oxidation state for the central metal ion in the complex may discourage dissociative activation even for anionic complexes as appears to be the case for OsX₆²⁻ (X = halide) where evidence for associative activation has been presented⁶⁸. Reactions of square-planar complexes of Au^{III} are significantly much more associative than for the analogous complexes of isoelectronic Pt^{II}⁶⁹. This appears from the observed effect of the nature of the entering nucleophile on the rate which is much more pronounced for Au^{III} than for Pt^{II} and the *k*_Y path for the generally observed two-term rate law for reactions of square-planar complexes being much more important for Au^{III} than for Pt^{II} (S being solvent) :

$$k_{\text{obs}} = k_{\text{S}} + k_{\text{Y}} [\text{Y}] \quad (5)$$

Since the *k*_Y path is much more important for Au^{III} the effect of overall charge on the complex on the rate is also more significant for Au^{III} than for Pt^{II}⁷⁰. Significant associative character of reactions of Au^{III} has also been inferred from the observed solvent dependence of the rate⁷¹. The observed Δ*V*_{k_S}[‡] and Δ*V*_{k_Y}[‡] values⁷² for ligand replacement reactions of Pt^{II} complexes are significantly negative which is in accord with the general mechanism proposed earlier based on first systematic studies on several complexes of Pt^{II}⁷³. But the rather insensitivity of the rate on the overall charge on the Pt^{II} complex suggests that both bond-making and bond-breaking make significant contributions as expected from the proposed mechanism⁷³. In accordance with the proposed mechanism as the bond to the departing ligand breaks there is concurrent transformation of two weak bonds Pt...S/Pt...Y into normal bonds thus accounting for a net decrease in molar volume and hence the observed negative Δ*V*[‡]. For chloride anation of the Pd^{II} complex Pd(Et₄dien)(H₂O)²⁺, the Δ*V*[‡] is -3.0 ± 0.2 cm³ mol⁻¹ and this negative value and other evidences suggest I_a process⁷⁴. For Pt(H₂O)₄²⁺, the rate of replacement of H₂O by DMSO is comparable to the water exchange rate constant (*k*_{ex}) under comparable conditions; but anation of the Pt^{II} complex by Cl⁻, Br⁻, I⁻ and SCN⁻ occurs by much faster rates with significant dependence on the nature of the entering nucleo-

phile. These observations suggest a changeover of the mechanism from I_d to I_a with the nature of the entering nucleophile⁷⁵.

The presently accepted general mechanism of substitution in square-planar complexes followed from the first systematic studies which established the influence of the nature of the entering ligand on the rate and the kinetic nature of the *trans-effect* and that an entering ligand which is known to have high *trans-effect* also leads to a fast rate of substitution even in the absence of a strong *trans-effect* ligand in the Pt^{II} complex⁷³. Similar studies on complexes of Pd^{II} have shown the absence of such effect (kinetic *trans-effect*) in the Pd^{II} complexes⁷⁶. The two-term rate law has been shown to be generally valid in many substitution studies reported by the present author⁷⁷.

Formation of $[\text{Pd}_2\text{Cl}_2(\mu\text{-dppm})_2(\mu\text{-NSO}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{R})]$ from $[\text{Pd}_2\text{Cl}_2(\mu\text{-dppm})_2]$ and $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{R})\text{SO}_2\text{N}_3$ in CH_2Cl_2 solvent obeys a Hammett relationship with $\rho = +1.39$ which is consistent with electrophilic attack of the arenosulfonylazide on the complex⁷⁸. An associative process involving little bond-breaking but considerable ordering of solvent and reactants has been proposed. Ethylene exchange is faster for $[\text{PtCl}_3(\eta^2\text{-C}_2\text{H}_4)]^-$ than for *trans*- $[\text{PtCl}_2(\eta^2\text{-C}_2\text{H}_4)(\text{MeOH})]$ and an entropically controlled associative process has been proposed⁷⁹. Associative process also operates for phosphine exchange in $[\text{Pd}(\text{CH}_2\text{COCR}_3)(\text{Cl})(\text{PPh}_3)_2]$ ($\text{R} = \text{H}$ or Me)⁸⁰. Substitution of X in the cubane cluster $[\text{Fe}_4\text{S}_4\text{X}_4]^{2-}$ ($\text{X}^- = \text{PhS}^-$ or Cl^-) by $\text{Et}_2\text{NCS}_2^-$ occurs via a dissociative process⁸¹.

Formation and ligand exchange also come under the category of ligand replacement process. Replacement of a metal-bound aqua-ligand by any other ligand in aqueous solution is generally referred to as formation reaction, also is called anation if the entering ligand is an anion. Similar reactions are known for solvated metal ions in other solvents, viz. $\text{MS}_6 + \text{L} \rightarrow \text{MS}_5\text{L} + \text{S}$. The general mechanism of formation reaction has been elaborately discussed in literature⁸² and such substitution at labile metal centres is through the operation of the Eigen-Wilkins mechanism⁸³. This visualizes formation of an outer-sphere complex (os) which forms the product by dissociative (I_d) or associative (I_a) paths :

X = solvent (H_2O or S) for a formation reaction. Various criteria have been used to distinguish between associative and dissociative processes in different systems⁸⁴. Some

general results are that such reactions of $\text{Ni}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{2+}$ are dissociative but those of $\text{Fe}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{3+}$ and $\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{3+}$ are associative, but for $\text{M}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5(\text{OH})^{2+}$ ($\text{M} = \text{Fe}, \text{Cr}$) the reactions are dissociative and the plausible reasons for such variations have been proposed. The various criteria used are effect of the entering ligand, magnitude of the activation parameters, such as ΔS^\ddagger and ΔH^\ddagger , and also ΔV^\ddagger , isokinetic trend, *LFER*, etc. Of much significance is formation of ternary complexes and of complexes of chelating and of macrocyclic ligands many of which emerged from the present author's laboratory⁸⁵. The ΔV^\ddagger ⁸⁶ criterion has been used to indicate change in mechanism from I_d in cases of Co^{II} and Ni^{II} to I_a for Mn^{II} with Fe^{II} being borderline for solvent exchange in $\text{M}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{2+}$ and $\text{M}(\text{MeOH})_6^{2+}$. A change of mechanism from associative to dissociative for Cr^{III} and Ga^{III} respectively with Fe^{III} being borderline for solvent exchange of MS_6^{3+} ($\text{M} = \text{Cr}, \text{Fe}, \text{Ga}$; $\text{S} = \text{H}_2\text{O}, \text{DMF}, \text{DMSO}, (\text{MeO})_3\text{PO}$) based on observed ΔV^\ddagger values has been reported⁸⁷.

Measurements of ΔV^\ddagger and of ΔS^\ddagger have been of use⁸⁸ in providing useful mechanistic information on the rapid formation of $[\text{M}(\text{TPPS})(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{NO})]$ from $[\text{M}(\text{TPPS})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ ($\text{M} = \text{Fe}^{\text{II}}, \text{Co}^{\text{II}}$) and NO . The behavior differs from that of the analogous reaction of $[\text{Fe}(\text{TPPS})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^+$. Several such and related processes have been reviewed⁸⁹.

Activation volume (ΔV^\ddagger) for Cl^- and Br^- anation of $[\text{Pt}(\text{L-L})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^x$ ($\text{L-L} = \text{en}, 2\text{tu}, 2\text{Me}_2\text{tu}, \text{cis- and trans-}(\text{NO}_2)_2$) are in the range of -4 to $-11 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ as expected for an associative process⁹⁰. Other fairly recent studies are of $[\text{Pt}(\text{en})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{2+}$ with thiosemicarbazide^{91a}, glycolic acid^{91b} and adenosine^{91c}, and of $[\text{Pd}(\text{L-His})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{2+}$ with a series of nucleobases, nucleosides, nucleotides and dinucleotides⁹².

The ΔV^\ddagger value for $k_{\text{ex}}^{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ of $\text{Eu}_{\text{aq}}^{2+}$ ion⁹³ is $-11.3 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ and related data have been reported for $[\text{Al}(\text{sal})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]^+$ ⁹⁴, $[\text{UO}_2(\text{ox})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{2-}$ and $[\text{UO}_2(\text{OAc})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{95}$ and $\text{MO}_{2\text{aq}}^{2+}$ ($\text{M} = \text{U}, \text{Np}, \text{Pu}$)⁹⁶. Helm and Merbach⁹⁷ reviewed the complimentary application of simulation and experiment to an understanding of these processes. Density functional theory calculations suggest⁹⁸ an *A* mechanism for $k_{\text{ex}}^{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ of $\text{Ti}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{3+}$ but *D* mechanism for $\text{Ti}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5(\text{OH})^{2+}$. Calculations have shown⁹⁹ that $\text{Ru}(\text{NH}_3)_5(\text{H}_2\text{O})^{3+}$ undergoes water replacement by an I_d process. Oxygen exchange of MO_4^- ($\text{M} = \text{Tc}, \text{Re}$) with that of water in solution¹⁰⁰ follows the rate-law,

$$k_{\text{obs}} = k_0 + k_{\text{H}} [\text{H}^+]^2 \quad (7)$$

For TcO_4^- , the k_0 path is unaffected by added citrate but a dramatic acceleration has been seen for ReO_4^- . ¹⁹F-NMR

have confirmed⁹⁵ five different pathways needed to describe F⁻ exchange of [UO₂F_x(OAc)_y]^(2-x-y) (x = 1 or 2, y = 1-3). Acetate exchange has also been studied. $k_{\text{ex}}^{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ of [Gd(dota)-(H₂O)]⁻ is 10 times smaller in 1 M acid than in neutral solution¹⁰¹.

In the formation of 1 : 1 complexes in the reactions of *N,N'*-*p*-chlorophenylthiosemicarbazide with Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} in DMF solution in presence of acetate, studied by stopped-flow spectrophotometry, two types of behaviour have been observed¹⁰². While for Ni^{II} a normal behaviour has been observed with the rate increasing with increasing concentration of the ligand (L) with

$$k_{\text{obs}} = (k_1' T_{\text{OAc}} + k_1'') T_{\text{L}}, \quad (8)$$

an inverse dependence of rate on ligand concentration has been observed in cases of Co^{II} and Cu^{II},

$$k_{\text{obs}} = k_2' T_{\text{OAc}} + k_2'' / T_{\text{L}} \quad (9)$$

Appropriate schemes have been proposed¹⁰² for such behavior.

Ligand dissociation and ligand replacements are often catalysed by electrophiles and nucleophiles^{8b}. For dissociation of metal chelates of ligands having 'free' (unbound) basic sites as in the cases of ligands like oxalate, malonate, acetylacetonate, biguanides, etc., binding of an electrophile like H⁺ or M^{m+} to the free basic site in a pre-equilibrium prior to chelate ring opening is visualized and this facilitates the chelate ring opening and its dissociation from the metal centre. The generality of such a mechanism has been established from several systematic studies carried out in the author's laboratory¹⁰³. Dependence of rate constant for acid catalysed dissociation of metal chelates on various acidity functions enabled to infer the type of transformation (associative or dissociative) of the protonated conjugate acid resulting from the complex¹⁰⁴. Cases of nucleophilic catalysis are also known and this is particularly true for square-planar complexes of Pd^{II} and Pt^{II} where in many cases both electrophilic and nucleophilic catalysis has been observed¹⁰⁵. Cases are also known of inverse dependence on acid concentration, observed in systems where the conjugate base form of the complex is the more reactive species¹⁰⁶. In the intramolecular redox decomposition of Ag(ethylenedibiguanide)³⁺ retardation of rate with increase in acid concentration has been observed¹⁰⁷. For reduction in acid medium of some substitution-inert Co^{III} complexes by N₂H₅⁻, HONH₃⁺, HCOOH acceleration of the reduction by acid has been observed¹⁰⁸; these systems show features of inner-sphere reactions for which a novel mechanism has been proposed that visualizes a proton-bridged intermediate in-

volving the Co^{III} complex and the reductant^{108f}. The metal ion assisted (metal = Hg^{II}, Ag^I, Tl^{III}, etc.) dissociation of complexes having M-X bond (X⁻ = Cl⁻, Br⁻, I⁻, N₃⁻, SCN⁻, etc.) and of M-F catalysed by H⁺, Al³⁺, etc., also belong to this category of electrophilic catalysis¹⁰⁹. In an investigation on the Hg^{II}-catalysed aquation of Co(dmgH)₂(NCS)₂ evidence has been furnished for the operation of an S_E2 mechanism; this involves synchronous Co-NCS bond breaking and Hg-SCN bond formation without the formation of an intermediate Co-NCS-Hg of detectable stability¹¹⁰. Acid-catalysed bridge-cleavage in [(H₃N)₅Ru(μ-X)Ru(NH₃)₄(μ-X)Ru(SCN)(NH₃)₄]⁶⁺ involves¹¹¹ associative H₂O attack on middle Ru^{III}.

The Co^{III} promoted ester aminolysis in the formation of peptide linkages^{112a}, mechanisms of action of purple acid phosphatases^{112b,c}, the role of metal ions in phosphate diester hydrolysis¹¹³ and the more general phenomenon of metal ion functional group cooperativity in peptidases and nucleases¹¹⁴ have been reviewed. Metal ion catalyzed DNA and RNA hydrolyses have been reviewed¹¹⁵ and studied¹¹⁶.

Electrophilic catalysis in isomerization¹¹⁷ and racemization¹¹⁸ reactions are also known, as also acceleration of racemization by anions (nucleophiles)¹¹⁹. Ion-pairing often leads to rate retardation as in the aquation of IrCl₆³⁻ by many M³⁺ (M = Ga, Fe, Ce, Eu) ions¹²⁰, although the aquation is considerably accelerated by In³⁺¹²¹ and the usual Hg²⁺. Aquation of the very inert OsF₆²⁻ is catalysed by Zr^{IV}. But surprisingly the rate constants for the Zr^{IV}-catalysed aquation of OsF₆²⁻, ReF₆²⁻, PtF₆²⁻ and PF₆⁻ are the same under identical conditions. Comparison with the rate constant for depolymerization of polynuclear Zr^{IV} species in the aqueous solutions shows that this depolymerization process in generating the reactive Zr^{IV} species (which acts as the catalyst) is indeed the rate-determining step¹²².

Substitution including ligand exchange in Pt^{IV} complexes is catalyzed by Pt^{II}¹²³. As a rule, substitution at a metal centre is markedly catalysed by a species of the metal in a higher or a lower oxidation state¹²⁴. An electron transfer mechanism operates in such cases. Co(phen)₃²⁺ catalyses racemization of Co(phen)₃³⁺ by outer-sphere redox mechanism¹²⁵. In the reaction of Co^{III}(NH₃)₅L with CN⁻ which is known to be catalysed by Co^{II} operation of outer-sphere electron transfer mechanism leads to formation of Co(CN)₆³⁻, while operation of inner-sphere mechanism leads to Co^{III}(CN)₅L, depending upon the nature of L (non-bridging or bridging)^{124b}.

Isomerization and racemization reactions

The mechanism of *cis* ⇌ *trans* isomerization of com-

plexes of Pd^{II} and Pt^{II} has been the subject of much study and controversy. Significant and valuable information has been provided by studies of Favez and coworkers¹²⁶ on *cis-trans* isomerization of PtX₂(PR₃)₂ (X = halide) in presence of PR₃ (catalyst) in CH₂Cl₂ using ³¹P-NMR technique. With this and other spectroscopic techniques they identified in solution both four-coordinate and five-coordinate species and based on their findings they proposed the following mechanism (L = PR₃) :

Isomerization of [Pt(N-O)(L)Cl] type complexes (N-O = glycinate, sarcosinate, *N,N*-dimethylglycinate, etc.; L = DMSO) is catalysed by Cl⁻ and takes place through formation of a five-coordinate intermediate Pt(N-O)(L)Cl₂⁻. The isomerization involves the change *trans*-(N-Pt-Cl) to *cis*-(N-Pt-Cl)¹²⁷. A dissociative mechanism involving formation of a five-coordinate intermediate is involved in the *trans-cis* isomerization of Cr(A-A)₂(H₂O)₂⁻ (A-A = oxalate, malonate)¹²⁸, but the generation of the five-coordinate intermediate is through loss of a H₂O for the oxalato complex but chelate ring opening for the malonate complex favored due to larger chelate ring size in the latter. The observed ΔV^\ddagger values have been reconciled with the proposed mechanism. The observed ΔV^\ddagger value of +7.9 cm³ mol⁻¹ (in 0.005 M HClO₄) for *trans* → *cis* isomerization of Co(en)₂(OAc)(H₂O)²⁺ is in agreement with a dissociative change¹²⁹ through a five-coordinate intermediate resulting presumably by loss of the H₂O. The *mer* ⇌ *fac* isomerization of Co(dien)(L)(H₂O)₂³⁺ (L = H₂O, NH₃, etc.) also takes place by a dissociative process generating a *thp* intermediate due to loss of a H₂O¹³⁰. Linkage isomerization of M(NH₃)₅(ONO)²⁺ (M = Co, Rh, Ir)¹³¹ and of Co(NH₃)₅(SCN)²⁺¹³² occur by intramolecular mechanism without any loss (dissociation) of a ligand and the observed negative values of ΔV^\ddagger can be reconciled with this mechanism. In contrast, linkage isomerization of Pd(Et₄dien)(XCN)⁺ (X = S, Se) to Pd(Et₄dien)(NCX)⁺ occurs at rates identical to the rates of solvolysis of the complexes¹³³. The change therefore involves [S=solvent molecule],

S = solvent molecule

Some fairly recent studies on isomerization reactions are the photoisomerization of Co(L)(SO₃)(H₂O)⁺ (L = (14)aneN₄ or Me₆(14)dienN₄)¹³⁴, interconversion of (O,O) and (O, alkene)-bonded forms of the square-planar Pt(dmpde)(L)(L = diallyl malonate)¹³⁵ and epimerization of Λ -Co(S-dap)(en)₂²⁺¹³⁶.

Racemization reactions are of much importance since the early days of coordination chemistry. While Ni(phen)₃²⁺ racemizes by an intermolecular (dissociative) mechanism the corresponding reactions of M(phen)₃²⁺ (M = Fe, Co, Cr) are intramolecular¹³⁷. Use of ΔV^\ddagger criterion in elucidating the mechanism of racemization for several anionic and cationic *tris*-chelate complexes of Cr^{III} has been reported¹³⁸. Evidence points to chelate ring opening for anionic complexes like Cr(ox)₃³⁻ and Cr(LL)(ox)₂⁻ (LL = bipy, phen) while the cationic complexes Cr(LL)₃³⁺ and Cr(LL)₂(ox)⁺ racemize by a *twist mechanism* without any chelate ring opening or any ligand dissociation. Bailar and co-workers¹³⁹ reported that in the solid state *cis-α*-[Co(trien)Cl₂]⁺ (chloride salt) undergoes slow thermal isomerization to the *cis-β*-isomer at *ca.* 150° as permissible by the trigonal Bailar twist mechanism¹⁴⁰, but due to presence of a quadridentate ligand the tetragonal (rhombic) twist (Ray-Dutt twist) mechanism¹⁴¹ is not permissible in this case. This result provided a rare and unequivocal demonstration of the operation of the Bailar twist in an isomerization process. It has been shown¹⁴² that in the solid state, at temperatures well below 200° racemization of *l-cis*-[M(en)₂Cl₂]⁺ (chloride salts, M = Co, Cr) takes place at a slow but conveniently measurable rate without any *cis* ⇌ *trans* conversion which is in agreement with the Ray-Dutt twist¹⁴¹ and not the Bailar twist¹⁴⁰ which latter would allow isomerization along with racemization. A dissociative mechanism involving an intermediate of coordination number 5 is also excluded as this will also lead to isomerization and racemization¹⁴³ as in the operation of the Bailar twist.

Electron transfer reactions

Another class of reactions are the electron transfer reactions which are broadly of two types, viz. those with a net chemical change as in a typical redox process, e.g. Fe²⁺ + Ce⁴⁺ → Fe³⁺ + Ce³⁺, and those without a net chemical change as in an electron exchange reaction between two different oxidation states of an element, e.g. Fe_{aq}³⁺ + *Fe_{aq}²⁺ ⇌ Fe_{aq}²⁺ + *Fe_{aq}³⁺. Two different general mechanisms are known for electron transfer reactions, viz. *the outer-sphere mechanism* and *the inner-sphere mechanism* as proposed originally by Taube¹⁴⁴. Based on sound theoretical approach Marcus evaluated the different components that contribute to the overall ΔG° for an outer-sphere reaction and derived

an equation (*Marcus cross-relation*)¹⁴⁵ for calculating theoretically the rate constant for an outer-sphere electron transfer reaction from the exchange rate constants and equilibrium constant for the overall reaction, and its satisfactory validity has since then been tested in a number of systems,

Agreement between the experimental and calculated rate constants has often been considered as strong evidence for outer-sphere redox process. But there is evidence that a type of Marcus relationship may be applied to inner-sphere redox reactions also¹⁴⁶. A modification of the Marcus equation has been proposed¹⁴⁷ for very exo- and endothermic atom-transfer reactions. Mechanisms (including theoretical studies)¹⁴⁸ have been examined for oxygen atom transfer from Mo^{VI} to S^{IV}¹⁴⁸, from N^V to Ru^{III}¹⁴⁹ and Ru^V to S^{II}¹⁴⁹, Mo^{VI} to P^{III}¹⁵⁰, from S^{IV}^{151,152} to V^V, As^V, and Sb^V¹⁵² to Re^V. It has been suggested¹⁵³ that proteins have evolved in such a way that redox-centre proximity is sufficient to permit rapid long distance (up to 14 Å) *electron tunneling* through the protein. Studies on rather simple metal complexes continue and a fairly recent study is on Ru^{III} complexes¹⁵⁴. Reduction of Ru(L)(trien)⁺ (H₂L = 3,6-dihydroxy-1,4-benzoquinone) by 2 mol Ti_{aq}³⁺ to produce Ru(H₂L')(trien)⁺ (H₂L' = 3,6-dihydroxy-1,4-hydroquinone (reduction is not of the Ru^{III} centre but of a bound ligand) proceeds through an intermediate, both the formation and decay of which involve outer-sphere electron transfer¹⁵⁴. Rate constants for the *comproportionation* reaction,

show¹⁵⁵ a linear dependence on $-\Delta G^\circ$, varied by substitution in bipy and terpy. Various redox systems involving reactions of inorganic oxidants and reductants with inorganic and organic reductants and oxidants respectively have been studied fairly extensively by various groups of Indian workers^{156a}. A short review on mechanistic aspects of metal ion catalysis in oxidation by Ce^{IV} has appeared^{156b}.

Oscillating reactions

Since this article is meant for an issue of the *JICS* to be published in honour of Professor R. P. Dasgupta who made salient contributions on oscillating reactions, it would be appropriate to conclude by a brief mention of some recent developments in the field, but not necessarily involving metal complexes.

Periodic polymerization of acrylonitrile, added to a *Belousov-Zhabotinsky* (B-Z) reaction, is initiated¹⁵⁷ by the malonyl radical and terminated by BrO₂, with periodic

termination of the polymer chain dominating periodic initiation. The induction period in a B-Z reaction to which a methyl ketone is added is directly related to its enolization constant¹⁵⁸. Additional aspects of the B-Z reaction studied include CO₂ evolution from reactions of Ce^{IV} and malonic or bromomalonic acids¹⁵⁹, H-D isotope effects¹⁶⁰, bromination of malonic, bromomalonic, tartronic and ethanetetracarboxylic acids¹⁶¹, mixed mode periodic oscillations¹⁶², etc. Modification by oxygen of oscillations in the *Bray-Liebhaftsky* (B-L) reaction (H₂O₂ decomposition catalysed by IO₃⁻ and I₂ in acid) involves iodide oxidation¹⁶³. MoO₄²⁻ decreases the induction period and increases the average frequency of B-L oscillations¹⁶⁴.

Other iodate-containing oscillating systems studied include Fe(CN)₆⁴⁻-IO₃⁻-SO₃²⁻ in which buffers were used to control frequency¹⁶⁵. Large amplitude pH oscillations were seen when Mn²⁺ was added to the BrO₃⁻-SO₃²⁻-H⁺ system¹⁶⁶. CO₂ evolution from the H₂O₂-HSO₃⁻-HCO₃⁻ system plays a critical role in whether or not chaotic or simple periodic oscillation is seen¹⁶⁷. Other oscillators studied include Fe^{III}-nitrate catalysed oxidation of ethanol¹⁶⁸. In the presence of Cu^{II} catalysts oxidations of SCN⁻ or S₂O₈²⁻ by H₂O₂ or S₂O₈²⁻ display oscillations and bistability¹⁶⁹. The S₂O₈²⁻-ClO₂⁻-S²⁻ oscillating system has also been reported¹⁷⁰. Theoretical¹⁷¹ and modelling¹⁷² aspects of oscillating systems continue to receive attention.

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